

Assessing the Impact of Homestay Tourism on Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Chitwan and Nawalparasi, Nepal

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Abstract

The homestay industry is a growing sector in Nepal, where family members frequently participate in its operation. This industry is closely linked to promoting tourism in Nepal. Homestays hold substantial potential to improve local livelihoods and boost tourism. However, economic disparities among different homestays and their varying effects on household income remain unexplored. This research investigates the financial contributions of homestays, specifically from the Tharu, Bote, and Magar communities, and compares their economic benefits. It emphasizes how tourism can promote economic empowerment and better living standards, especially in rural Nepal. The goals are to compare the economic advantages of these three homestays and evaluate their influence on household income.

A quantitative research design is used to collect data from the owners of two hundred ten homestays by administering a survey instrument. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the collected data, and Principal Component Analysis was employed to assess changes in the income status of homestays.

Our results show that the Tharu community homestay earned the most significant economic progress, primarily due to consumer-oriented marketing strategies and stronger customer relationship management. The family members participating in the homestay business reported a 25–40% increase in their yearly income, and a clear positive link was found between the growth of homestay businesses and overall community economic development. Our study benefits homestay investors, young researchers, businessmen, academics, and students to understand the importance of the homestay business in improving the economic condition of family members and the community.

Keywords: *community homestay, economic impact, household economy, Madi municipality, tourism*